

Live Reviews Information Document

Live Reviews are topic-centered, interactive preprint review sessions that are live-streamed via Zoom for open-access scientific manuscripts that have not yet been through editorial peer review. These events are designed to be inclusive by allowing structured and constructive discussions around preprints and encouraging diverse methods of participation.

The Live Reviews are hosted by one or two facilitators from the PREreview team with experience in mediating video calls. Together, optionally with a topic expert, they guide participants through a constructive discussion of a preprint following structured questions that encourage diverse methods of participation and make it easier to record and later collate the feedback into a final, collaborative review.

Researchers—or anyone interested in joining the discussion—join from all over the world to collaborate on improving a preprint, build their network, and meet globally renowned experts. Preprint authors are also invited to join and asked to remain silent during the first two-thirds of the call unless asked a question by a participant. In previous events, we witnessed authors changing their analysis in real-time to respond to a comment and sharing the output with everyone at the end of the call. It was a fantastic experience that gave us hope for the future of knowledge exchange!

After the call, our team works with participants who are interested in helping to collate the fruits of the discussion into a full report that is then openly shared on [PREreview](#) associated with a unique digital object identifier (DOI). Final review authors also have the option to be recognized for their work and named as authors on the published PREreview linked with their [ORCID iD](#).